

GridFTP Protocol

Combined with Data Grid use for Sharing Files

Mrs. P. M. Chawan
pmchawan@vjti.org.in

Mr. Nitin R. Gavai
nitinseven@gmail.com
Computer Technology Dept.
VJTI, Mumbai

Ms. Mamta Meena
manilu0585@gmail.com

Abstract: Increases in mobile device processing power, storage capacity, and connectivity have led to a rapid rise in mobile device use. But it is due to wireless network limit, unstable characteristic and restricted storage space, so mobile users face challenges in establishing connections with other users for sharing video files. To address this issue, we propose an architecture that uses GridFTP protocol to establish a video sharing platform for mobile devices, combined with a data grid to help analyze and classify videos. We hope our system be a convenient sharing video way in wireless network, and promote more people use wireless devices.

Keywords: Data Grid, GridFTP, Mobile Grid, XML, P2P Network.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, mobile devices were just cell-phones that had conversation and message functions. The gradual progress of time led to PDAs, Smart Phones, and laptops, among others. Now, anyone can have these mobile devices for business or amusement. Though the wireless network is not mature at present, some improvements in processing power, storage capacity and connectivity have been made in recent years.

According to the report of eTForecasts [11], the number of people who used wireless network came to 200 million in 2004 from 79 million in 2001. Even has the possibility to grow to 779 million in 2010. Because wireless users increase and the rapid growth of the wireless communication that promote huge amount of manufacturing investment in the development of wireless devices. Provide more convenient and friendly applications for mobile devices have popularized them among users. Already, wireless devices are no longer used for communication only; they can take pictures, record video, play games, and visit the Internet sites. We can predict that wireless networks will be popular both at work and at home worldwide in the near future and they will become a part of people's everyday life.

Network developed and photographic equipments in widespread use that let making video clips popular. The network inhabitants from the traditional information receivers turn to the information promulgators. Internet users need a place to share their video clips. YouTube saw their demand and becomes the pioneer of video sharing website. Users can establish personal theaters,

movie issue stations, and news stations in YouTube to substitution tradition communication media. But many wireless users can not glance over heartily because wireless network limit and unstable characteristic. Therefore we want to aim at the wireless network to provide a platform similar YouTube. Let wireless network users also can share and watch videos to their heart's content. In this paper, we build a video sharing platform in wireless environment. And we constructed a Grid server to store videos [5] [6] [12], and to provide its computing power for converting various kinds format of videos to flash. Users connect to our servers to select videos and download them through GridFTP protocol.

BACKGROUND

Data Grids

Many scientific and engineering applications require access to large amounts (terabytes and petabytes) of distributed data. The size and number of these data collections has been growing rapidly in recent years and will continue to grow as new experiments and sensors come on-line, the costs of computation and data storage decrease and performance increases, and new computational science applications are developed.

Data Grids [1] [2] [3] [10] are grid computing systems that deal with data. They are built on next-generation computing infrastructures, providing intensive computation and analysis of shared large-scale databases, from hundreds of terabytes to petabytes,

across widely distributed scientific communities.

We adopted the Globus Toolkit as our Data Grid Infrastructure. The Data Grid environment provides solutions for security, video and data management, as well as information services [3] [7]. Java CoG (Commodity Grid Kit) [10] combines Java technology with Grid Computing to develop advanced Grid services and basic Globus video accessibility. It allows easier and more rapid application development by encouraging collaborative code reuse and avoiding duplication of effort among problem-solving environments, science portals, Grid middleware, and collaborative pilots.

THE GLOBUS TOOLKIT

The term Grid computing refers to the merging computational and networking infrastructure that is designed to provide pervasive, uniform and reliable access to data, computational, and human resources distributed over wide area environments [15]. Grid services allow scientists at locations throughout the world to share data collection instruments such as particle colliders, compute resources such as supercomputers and clusters of workstations, and community datasets stored on network caches and hierarchical storage systems. The Globus Toolkit developed within the Globus project provides middleware services for Grid computing environments. Major components include the Grid Security Infrastructure (GSI), which provides public-key-based authentication and authorization services; resource management services, which provide a language for specifying application requirements, mechanisms for immediate and advance reservations of Grid resources, and for remote job management; and information services, which provide for the distributed publication and retrieval of information about Grid resources. Data Grid services complement and build on these components. For example, the GridFTP transfer service and the replica management service described in the rest of this paper use GSI for authentication and authorization. Higher-level data replication services can use the information service to locate the “best” replica and the resource management service to reserve the computational, network, and storage resources required by a data movement operation.

EXTENSIBLE MARKUP LANGUAGE (XML)

The Extensible Markup Language (XML) is a W3C-recommended [13] [14] general-purpose markup language for creating special-purpose markup languages capable of describing many different kinds of data. XML files can also contain data, as in a database. It is a simplified subset of the Standard Generalized Markup

Language (SGML) [13] [14]. Its primary purpose is to facilitate the sharing of data across different systems, particularly systems connected via the Internet.

As XML increases in importance, a series of standards is growing up around it, many defined by the World Wide Web Consortium. For example, XML Schema provides a notation for defining new element and document types; XML Path Language (XPath) provides a notation for selecting elements within XML documents; Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformation (XSLT) provides a notation for transforming XML documents from one representation to another; XQuery is becoming the standard query language for XML databases; Document Object Model (DOM) and Simple Application Program Interface (API) for XML (SAX) were developed to facilitate the handling of XML documents. These XML technologies allow XML documents to be converted into HTML, postscript, pdf, Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG), and other document formats.

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Our Mobile Grid system is a hard-wired Grid integrated with a wireless network and P2P Protocol, as shown in Figure 1. It consists of three parts: Grid Index Server, general Grid Server Nodes, and Client Mobile Devices. The Grid Index Server is responsible for client certification and dispatching clients to Grid Server Nodes. Grid Server Nodes handle managing client video lists, and serve as client bridges. Client devices include hard-wired and wireless devices. Clients download video using the GridFTP Protocol.

Figure 1. The system architecture

THE GRIDFTP SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK

The GridFTP implementation in the Globus Toolkit consists of a family of tools – the GridFTP server, client program, client library and the control libraries that manage the data and control connections of an FTP session.

Below, we briefly describe the main GridFTP modules that are of interest to us:

- **globus-url-copy:** This is the GridFTP client tool provided with the Globus Toolkit, which works with multiple protocols (http, https, ftp, gsiftp). It takes a source URL and a destination URL as the arguments. The number of parallel streams can be specified as an optional argument.
- **globus-gass-copy:** the **globus-url-copy** is a simple wrapper around the **globus-gass-copy** program. This consists of an API for copying data from a source to a destination, specified by URLs. The protocols supported are http, https, ftp and gsiftp.
- **globus-ftp-client:** This is the FTP client library that supports standard FTP commands such as get, put etc, as well as the GridFTP extensions such as third-party-transfer.
- **globus-ftp-control:** This is the low level GridFTP driver, consisting of a set of libraries that handle the control and data management. The data channel management is symmetric for client and server sides, i.e., both client and server access a common set of functions for data transfer.
- **GridFTP Server:** This is a “globussified” version of the **wu-ftpd** server. GridFTP control and data channel management functions are invoked from within the main server module.

Figure 2. GridFTP Layout

To add DRS functionality to the GridFTP framework, most of the significant changes were made to the **globus-ftp-control** libraries. Figure 2 gives a general idea about the dependencies and interactions between the various modules described above. Note that the Globus Toolkit is a considerably complex piece of software.

GRIDFTP FUNCTIONALITY

GridFTP functionality includes some features that are supported by FTP extensions that have already been standardized (RFC 959) but are seldom implemented in current systems. Other features are new extensions to FTP.

Grid Security Infrastructure and Kerberos support:

Robust and flexible authentication, integrity, and confidentiality features are critical when transferring or accessing files. GridFTP must support GSI and Kerberos authentication, with user controlled setting of various levels of data integrity and/or confidentiality. GridFTP implements the authentication mechanisms defined by RFC 2228, “FTP Security Extensions”.

Third-party control of data transfer:

To manage large datasets for distributed communities, we must provide authenticated *third-party* control of data transfers between storage servers. A third-party operation allows a user or application at one site to initiate, monitor and control a data transfer operation between two other sites: the source and destination for the data transfer. Our implementation adds Generic Security Services (GSS)-API authentication to the existing third-party transfer capability defined in the FTP standard.

Parallel data transfer:

On wide-area links, using multiple TCP streams in parallel (even between the same source and destination) can improve aggregate bandwidth over using a single TCP stream [10]. GridFTP supports parallel data transfer through FTP command extensions and data channel extensions.

Striped data transfer:

Data may be striped or interleaved across multiple servers, as in a DPSS network disk cache [11]. GridFTP includes extensions that initiate striped transfers, which use multiple TCP streams to transfer data that is partitioned among multiple servers. Striped transfers provide further bandwidth improvements over those achieved with parallel transfers. We have defined GridFTP protocol extensions that support striped data transfers.

Partial file transfer:

Some applications can benefit from transferring portions of files rather than complete files: for example, high-energy physics analyses that require access to relatively small subsets of massive, object-oriented physics database files. The best that the standard FTP protocol allows is transfer of the remainder of a file starting at a particular offset. GridFTP provides commands to support transfers of arbitrary subsets or regions of a file.

Automatic negotiation of TCP buffer/window sizes:

Using optimal settings for TCP buffer/window sizes can dramatically improve data transfer performance. However, manually setting TCP buffer/window sizes is an error-prone process (particularly for non-experts) and is often simply not done. GridFTP extends the standard FTP command set and data channel protocol to support both manual setting and automatic negotiation of TCP buffer sizes for large files and for large sets of small files.

Support for reliable and restartable data transfer:

Reliable transfer is important for many applications that manage data. Fault recovery methods are needed to handle failures such as transient network and server outages. The FTP standard includes basic features for restarting failed transfers that are not widely implemented. GridFTP exploits these features and extends them to cover the new data channel protocol.

THE GRIDFTP PROTOCOL IMPLEMENTATION

Our implementation of the GridFTP protocol supports partial file transfers, third-party transfers, parallel transfers and striped transfers. We do not yet support automatic negotiation of TCP buffer/window sizes. The implementation consists of two principal C libraries: the `globus_ftp_control_library` and the `globus_ftp_client_library`.

The `globus_ftp_control_library` implements the control channel API. This API provides routines for managing a GridFTP connection, including authentication, creation of control and data channels, and reading and writing data over data channels. Having separate control and data channels, as defined in the FTP protocol standard, greatly facilitates the support of such features as parallel, striped and third-party data transfers. For parallel and striped transfers, the control channel is used to specify a put or get operation; concurrent data transfer occurs over multiple parallel TCP data channels. In a third-party transfer, the initiator monitors or aborts the operation via the control channel, while data transfer is performed over one or more data channels between source and destination sites.

The `globus_ftp_client_library` implements the GridFTP client API. This API provides higher-level client features on top of the `globus_ftp_control_library`, including complete file get and put operations, calls to set the level of parallelism for parallel data transfers, partial file transfer operations, third-party transfers, and eventually, functions to set TCP buffer sizes.

MANAGEMENT

The administration system consists of three integrated parts: (1) Information Monitor, (2) Replica Manager, and (3) Data Transfer Service, as shown in Figure 3. Administrators can use the friendly GUI to control Grid Servers, check server information, manage replicas, and transfer data as rapidly as possible.

Administrators look up status of all grid server nodes by information manager system. All information on grid server nodes, such as CPU loading, free memory capacity, hard disk free space, and system bandwidth is collected and saved in the Information Database. Administrators can monitor the operational status of each machine through the System Information. Monitor being integrated into the Interface Manager. When unusual events occur, the System Information Monitor notifies the Administrator to respond appropriately, thus improving service satisfaction and productivity.

Replica management can create and delete replicas at specified storage sites. Most often, these replicas are exact copies of original files created only to harness certain performance benefits. A replica manager typically maintains a replica catalog containing replica site addresses and file instances.

The Replica Monitor helps administrators observe data log information on data lists in the Replica Manager Service. Data log attributes include Data Summary, Share Time, Owner, Access Frequency, etc. The Replica Manager periodically synchronizes data lists on all grid servers to ensure data list identical. If the access frequency of some files is high, the Replica Manager will save the files on grid servers, and delete them when access frequency is lower than a given threshold.

Data transfer management is responsible for data in data-intensive applications; it provides effective and secure transmission for users. Administrators can view files on grid servers through data transfer browser, and direct data transfer controller to carry out file actions such as moving, copying, refreshing, and moving to other directories

Figure 3. Administrator operations

VIDEO DOWNLOAD AND UPLOAD

In our scheme, after users log into the index server through hard-wired or wireless networks, they will be assigned to grid server nodes by the index server based on the loading on each server node. Users can look up the video databases to find out videos they want, and download the video from the server.

We also provide the sharing method, if users want to share videos to other users. Users only need to upload their video to our servers; the Video Format Converter will convert them to Flash format and enroll them in the video databases [8] [9]. All videos are transmitted using the GridFTP protocol. The video download and upload scenario is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Operations of client devices

DOWNLOAD STRATEGY

Our system is a video sharing system as well as Gnutella, Napster, and many peer-to-peer network systems. Users can download file which they want and upload the possessive file which other users need at the same time. Our destination is fast network sharing for let anyone can fast get any files. To attain to multi-point download and resume broken download, files are divided in full chunks of 9,728,000 bytes plus a remainder chunk. Furthermore, valid downloaded chunks are available for sharing before the rest of the file is downloaded, speeding up the distribution of large files throughout the network, as shown in Figure 5. The system is designed for users to search the videos for users need. We also designed a management interface, with an integrated data transfer service, replica manager, and information monitor to facilitate user operation of the system.

When uploads each chunks, sharer are gave a time T. If a chunk has not shared completely in the time, it will be gave to other people have this chunks to share. Avoid some sharer's network speed is too slow to cause the entire download speed to reduce (see Figure 6).

Figure 5. Download Strategy

Figure 6. Time of upload chunk is up

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a video sharing platform combine with Data Grid system for wireless devices. As a result of wireless network limit and unstable characteristic, we use the function that is like P2P communication and much more suitable for wireless devices to address the issue. File requester can collect the limited sharing traffic to increase download speed, and replaces immediately supplies the files origin. We use Data Grid system to handle some central problems, i.e., search file location and client certification. Data Grid is extendable, let us can easily connect with many store equipment to form a large-scale storage system. Our system also depend on its' computing power to classify, analyze, and convert various kinds of video files, to keep the files in the newest state at all times.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.S. Chang and J.S. Chang, "Adaptable Replica Consistency Service for Data Grids," *Third International Conference on Information Technology: new Generations (ITNG'06)*, pp. 646-651, 2006.
- [2] A.L. Chervenak and M. Cai "Applying Peer-to-Peer Techniques to Grid Replica Location Services", *Journal of Grid Computing*, 4(1), pp. 49-69, March 2006.
- [3] I. Foster, C. Kesselman, and S. Tuecke. "The Anatomy of the Grid: Enabling Scalable Virtual Organizations", *Int. J. of Supercomputer Applications and High Performance Computing*, 15(3), pp. 200-222, 2001.
- [4] C. Huang, F. Xu, and X. Hu, "Massive Data Oriented Replication Algorithms for Consistency Maintenance in Data Grids," *ICCS 2006, Part I, LNCS 3991*, pp. 838-841, 2006.
- [5] H.Y. Hsieh and R. Sivakumar, "On Using Peer-to-Peer Communication in Cellular Wireless Data Networks", *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 57-72, Jan., 2004.
- [6] M. Marzolla, M. Mordacchini, and S. Orlando. "Peer-to-Peer systems for discovering videos", *Parallel Computing*, doi:10.1016/j.parco.2007.02.006.
- [7] H. Stockinger, Asad Samar, Bill Allcock, Ian Foster, Koen Holtman, and Brain Tierney, "File and Object Replication in Data Grids," *Journal of Cluster Computing*, 5(3), pp. 305-314, 2002.
- [8] FFmpeg, <http://ffmpeg.mplayerhq.hu/>
- [9] FLVTool2, <http://rubyforge.org/projects/flvtool2/>
- [10] Globus Project, <http://www.globus.org/>
- [11] Internet Users by Country, eTForecasts's Products, http://www.etforecasts.com/products/ES_intusersv2.htm
- [12] P2P Networks, <http://ntrg.cs.tcd.ie/undergrad/4ba2.02-03/Intro.html>
- [13] VeriSign, <http://www.verisign.com/>
- [14] XML, <http://www.w3.org/XML/>
- [15] I. Foster, C. Kesselman (eds.). *The Grid: Blueprint for a New Computing Infrastructure*. Morgan Kaufmann, 1999.